

e-INVOICE/TAX INVOICE

Section A: Seller's Details

TIN:	1000039198
Legal Name:	LAXICON ENTERPRISES (U) LIMITED
Trade Name:	LAXICON ENTERPRISES (U) LIMITED
Address:	215 6 th Street, Industrial Area Nakawa KAMPALA KAMPALA CENTRAL DIVI KAMPALA CENTRAL DIVISION INDUSTRIAL AREA
Seller's Reference Number:	LX-39834-2022
Served by:	Laxicon

Section B: URA Information

Document Type:	Original
Issued Date:	12/02/2025
Time:	13:30:03
Device Number:	1000039198_01
Fiscal Document Number:	1241731229383
Verification Code:	75143296031775867044

Section C: Buyer's Details

TIN:	1027418142
Name:	MR. PETER NAGEM I

Section D: Goods & Services Details

No.	Item	Quantity	Unit Measure	Unit Price	Total	Tax Category
1.	Tororo Cement -OPC-CEM I / 42.5 N	10	BG-Bag	45,000	450,000	A

Section E: Tax Details

Tax Category	Net Amount	Tax Amount	Gross Amount
A: VAT-Standard (18%)	381,355.93	68,644.07	450,000

Section F: Summary

Net Amount:	381,355.93
Tax Amount:	68,644.07
Gross Amount:	450,000 Four hundred fifty thousand shillings only.

Payment Mode

Cash	450,000
Total Amount	450,000
Currency:	UGX
Number of Items:	1
Mode:	Online
Remarks:	

*** END OF e-INVOICE/TAX INVOICE ***